

Proto-respiration, manipulating the redox balance between water and oxygen

Johan Nygren, johanngrn@gmail.com

As is seen in a simple acid-base electrochemical cell, exclusion of protons shifts the redox balance between the dihydro and dioxide state of oxygen, creating a potential for electric current. The ability of very simple “proto cells” to manipulate this balance led to the origin of life. Filaments in general have the ability to structure water into a gel phase that excludes hydrogen ions. This gel also has the ability to selectively adsorb univalent cations like potassium, further excluding hydrogen ions. This gel is chemically inert, and stored electrical potential is released by liquifying the gel, causing the reaction $4 \text{OH}^- \rightarrow 2 \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{O}_2 + 4 \text{e}^-$ (anode). Cells evolved by positive selection to extract work from the electrochemical balance between water and oxygen, by storing and releasing hydroxide-rich gel, the protoplasm, Thomas Huxley’s “physical basis of life”.

Figure 1 Oxygen and water is a balance scale that can be tipped in either direction to store or release electricity. This is achieved by manipulating the ionic composition of water, by increasing or decreasing the hydrogen ion content.